

INTER-SESSIONAL ASSIGNMENTS OF CORRESPONDENCE STUDENTS AND THEIR ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to improving the content of the session tasks of the intermediate course on descriptive geometry for students of the correspondence course (special correspondence course) Department. As a result, the quality of control and consolidation of students' knowledge is improved.*

Keywords: *special correspondence department, semester, tasks of intermediate control, complex, knowledge, assessment, graphic tasks, graphic literacy, graphic work, graphic task, consciousness, thinking, thought, presentation, test, exercise and task, surface, multilateral, independent work, creative work, electronic platform, descriptive geometry.*

Meeting the needs of educational institutions of the public education system in teaching staff with higher education in preschool, primary, music, fine arts, foreign languages, areas of labor education, physical culture and other disciplines, providing educational institutions of districts and rural areas with highly qualified teaching staff and improving the quality of education by further improving the organization of their training system on the ground Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2017- In August, Resolution No. PP-3183 "on the organization of special correspondence departments of pedagogical profile in higher educational institutions" was adopted. [1]

The special correspondence department of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami has been defined as a basic higher educational institution for the formation of qualification requirements, curricula and programs in the areas of education, educational and teaching literature, a Council for the coordination of educational and methodological activities of higher educational institutions has been established under it, in which special correspondence departments have been created in the areas of pedagogy.

Adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About the organization of special correspondence departments in higher educational institutions in the direction of pedagogy", along with ensuring the needs of secondary schools, preschool and extracurricular educational institutions in highly qualified teaching staff, expands the opportunities for higher education for young people with secondary special education engaged in pedagogical activities. This, in turn, contributes to increasing the role and prestige of the teaching profession in society, including the orientation of young people to the teaching profession on a systematic basis. [2]

A distinctive feature of students studying by correspondence (special correspondence) Of course, it is that they independently master the material on the subject, mainly remotely. In order to learn, evaluate and consolidate their knowledge of how well they mastered science, a type of task set known as tasks between sessions was adopted. At the same time, in the intervals between

semesters (sessions), the student performs tasks showing the level of knowledge he has received in each subject, and passes them to the lecturer-speaker. For each subject, the student is individually given task options, a source of literature and methodological guidelines in advance.

To begin with, let's look at what a semester and a session are in higher education. As we know, each academic year in universities is divided into two semesters. Students take the final control and are evaluated in the subjects they have studied and mastered during each semester. This process is called a session. And in the correspondence section, it is the sentence "tasks of the inter-session interval" that is used. That is, he determines the solutions of tasks for each subject during the period between two semesters and sends them electronically (or sends them in the prescribed manner) to the responsible professor before the start of the semester.

The content of the tasks of the inter-session interval of the student in the process of studying by correspondence, the procedures for its implementation are reported in the work program of the discipline prepared for each subject. The content of the tasks of the inter-session interval should include materials on all topics reflected in the work program of the discipline. The teacher should provide the student with consultations, methodological recommendations, a list of used literature and other methodological assistance. On the basis of such didactic provision, each student independently performs tasks of the inter-session interval.

The following types of independent work are distinguished from the content of inter-session tasks: preparation of an abstract on a specific topic; execution of computational and graphic works; work on a layout, model and artwork; search for solutions to an existing problem in practice, preparation of discussion questions and tasks; preparation of a scientific article, theses and a report; solving non-standard tasks of practical content and creative work; testing-answers to test questions; exercises, examples and problem solving; analysis of experimental results; preparation of methodological developments, letters of recommendation; drawing graphic works; homework, etc. [3]

After completing the tasks of the inter-session interval, the student registers it at the appropriate department, and it is checked by specialists and evaluated in due course. The purpose of checking and evaluating students' knowledge is to fulfill the requirements established in the DCS, to ensure the quality of their knowledge, the level of development, to stimulate, increase their interest and responsibility in obtaining knowledge.

Currently, electronic platforms in all subjects have been developed and are constantly being improved for students studying at a special correspondence department. This electronic platform contains scientific programs, videos, presentations of each lecture, the content of the tasks of the inter-session period, methodological recommendations for its implementation, a bank of individual options for each student. But it is too early to talk about the full quality of these materials and conclude that the electronic platform is in demand among students and teachers.

In the science of descriptive geometry, methods of depicting objects located in three-dimensional space, on a two-dimensional plane or surface are investigated. It also studies the theoretical rules for constructing and reading drawings of geometric shapes and surfaces. The educational standard of the educational direction establishes that a future drawing teacher should be able to independently build orthogonal, axonometric and central projections of geometric shapes and surfaces, check positional, metric relations between geometric shapes and surfaces, possess engraving literacy in the requirements that he is obliged to master in this subject.

A person with graphic literacy can make any drawing and can read it. Therefore, based on the specifics of the disciplines of descriptive geometry and drawing, the content of the tasks of the inter-session interval will consist in performing graphic work, that is, in submitting a drawing. The knowledge gained by the student is determined by checking and evaluating the graphic works performed by him independently.

At this stage, it is necessary to correctly establish the purpose of checking and evaluating the student's knowledge and establish it. The verification of knowledge and its evaluation in their achievements also have the following disadvantages: misunderstanding of its tasks (functions); unjustified overestimation of its role in the educational process; turning verification and evaluation into the main goal of the lesson; using the same technology in the verification and evaluation of knowledge; allowing subjectivity in the assessment and lack of clear, reasonable criteria; when checking and evaluating students' knowledge, one should not forget about performing an important function that controls this process, educational.[4]

The above-mentioned "the use of the same technology in the verification and evaluation of knowledge", "the admission of subjectivity in the assessment and the lack of clear, reasonable criteria" disadvantages are obvious. That is, based on the nature of the educational process of the correspondence (special correspondence) department, there is a situation in the tasks of the inter-session interval when from one type of checks and assessments: the student is limited only to drawing a graphic task. However, due to the specifics of science, the main indicator is technical and graphic literacy. But we believe that it would also be advisable to effectively use other methods of checking and evaluating knowledge, given that in the correspondence department the audience does not communicate much live with the student and that the assimilation occurs mainly independently.

Today there are current, intermediate and final types of verification and assessment of students' knowledge. Well-known types of ongoing verification are: various forms of oral questioning, verification of written homework, written control (independent) tasks. However, along with such traditional forms, verification with the help of various punched cards is increasingly used, checking the completion of a task using a computer.[5] The reasonable use of other types of verification and assessment of knowledge for the full fulfillment of the minimum requirement established by the educational standard gives a positive effect.

We believe that checking and evaluating a student's knowledge of descriptive geometry by conducting oral questions and answers, receiving written answers to questions, solving problems that require partial or complete creative search, compiling and working on cases, drawing graphic tasks, and answering test questions will have a positive effect. Having studied a large amount of educational literature, analyzed it, and based on the requirements of the time, we found it expedient to compile, on the basis of an integrated approach, the content of the inter-session assignments of students of the correspondence (special correspondence) department on the subject of "Descriptive Geometry", revision in the following order and to test it in practice.

In addition, summarizing our methodological recommendations, in the correspondence (special correspondence) section, we formulated a structure – model of didactic provision of tasks of the inter-session interval on the subject of descriptive geometry in a certain sense. We believe that this model can be effectively used in teaching other subjects (Fig. 1).

1. Mastering science through answers to theoretical questions. In it, the student prepares a written answer to the questions asked in his version, and sends it to the lecture teacher

in electronic form (who, if desired, can also add an option in voice mode). This situation forces the student to read a book, and also develops his written and oral speech. He also teaches the student to work on educational literature, to reason, to observe, to compare, to draw conclusions, to develop his speech by oral presentation of the acquired knowledge. Speech (written and oral), which is the process of cognition of an individual, develops in harmony. As a result, the feelings inherent in the teacher are formed and consolidated in the student.

In addition, the student develops the ability to compose tasks and make cases, the drawing of which requires creative searches on the subject of geometry. Because a student of a correspondence (special correspondence) school is a person who works directly in a comprehensive school.

Here we must not forget that the content of the questions in an individual version should cover the content of each section or chapter of science. For example, in the 1st semester, each student must be asked one question from all the sections of the subject passed. Below is an example of this:

2. Mastering science through exercises and problem solving. At this stage, human activity increases in such cognitive processes as intuition, perception, memory, imagination, thinking, speech, imagination in psychology. It becomes possible to apply the theoretical data of the first stage in practice.

Fig. 1

Even to this day, students are working on various exercises, examples and tasks to gain full knowledge in mathematics, geometry, physics, chemistry, biology, native language and other subjects. Such cognitive activity contributes to the qualitative and full-fledged assimilation of the passed subject. At this stage, it is assumed that the student will develop various tasks on

descriptive geometry. The level of complexity of the tasks is not too high, i.e. simple enough for the answer to be fast. Structured tasks are performed by drawing drawings depending on the nature of the science. Therefore, the level of complexity of the graphic tasks of the second stage should be sharply different from the graphic works of the third stage. By solving such problems, the student gains knowledge in almost all aspects of science and masters them.

3. Grafik vazifalar chizish orqali fanni o'zlashtirish. Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, chizmalarni o'qish va ularni chiza olish malakasini egallagan, ya'ni grafik savodxon bo'lgan talaba ushbu fan yuzasidan to'laqonli bilimga ega bo'la oladi.

Graphic task-a task and its content determined by the normative documents of engineering graphics disciplines and to be performed by the student. A graphic task is defined as a task for students to master the subject and improve their graphic literacy.

Graphic work is a drawing performed by a student individually in compliance with the requirements of the standard. The performance of graphic work contributes to the improvement of the student's graphic literacy and the assimilation of the subject.

Graphic literacy is the level of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by a student when drawing up and reading drawings of geometric shapes and objects.

Ensuring the graphic literacy of a student is the most important task facing specialists in the discipline "Descriptive Geometry". Each student draws graphic tasks based on the requirements of the educational standard and the content of the topics set out in the work program on the subject. Each of them is provided with individual options. Methodical recommendations and tips on the implementation of the graphic task are given by the teacher. The content of graphic tasks and the degree of their complexity are determined on the basis of the scientific program and the decision of the scientific and methodological council of the department.

We have formulated the content of 10 graphic tasks for correspondence students on the subject of descriptive geometry. Each task contains no more than 3 graphical tasks.

4. Mastering science by example and solving problems that require partial or complete creative search. As you know, scientific and technical development is largely based on technical design. The development of technology is not complete without drawings. To do this, it is necessary to instill in the student (student) elements of a creative approach (design) in the process of learning to draw and when performing each graphic work. [6] it would be more efficient if the graphical tasks at the fourth stage were solved in such a way that creative research would be required. Perhaps this verification method could be applied to gifted students.

5. Master the science by answering the test questions. Although testing itself has many aspects of achievement, it cannot be fully applied to subjects that can be mastered by doing some practical work. That is, the rejection of other methods of testing knowledge and the introduction instead of them only the control work "drawing geometry", and not "drawing" it is not considered the right path for discipline. For subjects that have such a practical appearance, the most correct is the joint use of methods that require the performance of other practical work with the test method of checking the student's knowledge.

Based on the above points, it will be advisable to use a test evaluation method at the fifth stage. At this stage, the student will be able to test their theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as evaluate them. With the help of the test, the student not only gets the opportunity to test their knowledge in a short period of time, but also ensures the reliability of this knowledge. At this stage, separate test options for students should also be developed.

Test questions can be formulated both with the help of graded tests in a traditional or non-traditional (non-standard) way. The contents of non-standard tests are summarized below.

1. *Non-standard test tasks used to monitor and evaluate the degree to which students achieve the cognitive learning goal. [7]*

2. *Non-standard test tasks used to monitor and evaluate the degree to which students achieve an educational goal related to understanding.*

3. *Non-standard test tasks used in monitoring and evaluating the degree to which students achieve the educational goal of practical application of knowledge.*

4. *Non-standard test tasks used in the control and assessment of the degree of achievement by students of the educational goal concerning the preparation of the conclusion.*

5. *Monitor and evaluate the extent to which students achieve the learning goal related to analysis."*

6. *Control and assessment of the degree to which students achieve the goal of learning the synthesis of knowledge.*

7. *Monitoring and evaluation of the degree of achievement by students of the educational goal associated with the preparation of the conclusion.*

8. *You can also use tests such as closed and open tests.*

In order to improve the content of the inter-sessional assignments of students of the correspondence department on the basis of an integrated approach, the theoretical questions-answers, exercises-problem solving, graphic tasks, solving problems requiring creative search, as well as checking and evaluating the student's knowledge on test questions, offered by us, have a positive effect in practice. The above-mentioned five different concepts of knowledge testing and evaluation do not allow the student to acquire knowledge in the same way and, as a result, psychologically exhausted, tired, bored. Preparation for the assigned tasks arouses the student's interest in the subject and encourages him to master it enthusiastically.

REFERENCES

1. <http://lex.uz/docs/3299721>
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017- yil 9- avgustdagi "Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida pedagogika yo'nalishida maxsus sirtqi bo'limlarni tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi PQ-3183-sonli qarori.
3. Valiyev A., Ashirboyev A., Tashimov N. Chizma geometriya fanidan talabalarining mustaqil ishini tashkil etish, nazorat qilish va baholash me'zonlari. TDPU, 2018.
4. Mavlonova R., To'rayeva O., K.Xoliqberdiyev. Pedagogika. –T.: "O'qituvchi", 2010-159-bet..
5. Mavlonova R., To'rayeva O., K.Xoliqberdiyev. Pedagogika. –T.: "O'qituvchi", 2010-160-bet.
6. Valiyev A.N., Rahmatova I.I. O'quvchilarda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda loyihalash masalalarining o'rni. –T.: "Xalq ta'limi" jurnali, 2018-yil, 6-son. 38-bet.
7. Valiyev A.N., Amirqulov X.Q., Valiyeva B.N. Maxsus sirtqi bo'lim talabalarini o'qitishda darajali testlardan foydalanish. –T.: «Fizika va zamonaviy astronomiya: innovatsion o'qitishning yangi modellarini yaratish» mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. 2019 y. 245-247 betlar.